

CONTEMPORARY ASPECTS OF FETAL ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION IN PRENATAL DIAGNOSTICS

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ABSTRACT

Ultrasound (echography) has been used in pregnancy for over 60 years. Ultrasound diagnostics is the primary, and in early pregnancy, the only, method for visually assessing pregnancy progress. All civilized countries routinely conduct two to three ultrasound examinations of all pregnant women in the population (mass ultrasound screening). Experience shows that rational use of this method significantly improves pregnancy outcomes for both the fetus and the mother. The primary benefit of using ultrasound in obstetrics and gynecology is the prevention of children born with severe hereditary diseases and congenital malformations.

Relevance. Fetal ultrasound is one of the leading methods of modern prenatal diagnostics, enabling the early detection of congenital anomalies, functional disorders, and intrauterine growth retardation. In recent decades, advances in ultrasound technologies (including 3D/4D imaging and Doppler ultrasound) have significantly increased the diagnostic accuracy of this method.

Ultrasound examination in obstetrics and gynecology is considered a highly complex procedure in all civilized countries. The responsibility is extremely high: an incorrect ultrasound report can often have an impact on the life of the fetus, the health of the child, and the mother.

Despite the progress made, issues of early detection of pathologies, optimization of screening timing, and increasing the prognostic value of ultrasound markers remain pressing. This is especially important given the increasing incidence of metabolic and somatic disorders in pregnant women that affect fetal well-being.

Purpose of the study. To evaluate the current capabilities of ultrasound examination in prenatal diagnostics and determine its effectiveness in identifying fetal abnormalities at various stages of pregnancy.

Materials and methods. This prospective study monitored the pregnancy progression of 250 women undergoing follow-up at obstetric facilities in Fergana. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 40 years. Inclusion criteria included a singleton pregnancy and informed consent. Women with severe decompensated extragenital pathology or multiple pregnancies were excluded.

Depending on their clinical and anamnestic characteristics, all participants were divided into three groups: the first group consisted of pregnant women with a physiological course of gestation; the second group included patients with risk factors for the development of pregnancy complications (overweight, arterial hypertension, metabolic disorders); the third group consisted of women with established fetal pathology.

The primary examination method was fetal ultrasound, which was performed at standard screening times: in the first trimester (11-13 weeks), second trimester (18-22 weeks), and third trimester (30-34 weeks of pregnancy). The examination was performed using modern, expert-class ultrasound equipment.

During the study, a comprehensive ultrasound assessment of the fetus's condition was carried out, including fetometry, an assessment of the anatomical structures of the fetus to exclude congenital anomalies, and determination of the compliance of the fetus's size with the gestational age.

Additionally, blood flow was measured using Doppler ultrasound in the uterine arteries, umbilical artery, and middle cerebral artery of the fetus, allowing for an assessment of the uteroplacental and fetoplacental circulation. When indicated, cardiotocography was performed to assess the functional status of the fetus.

Statistical analysis of the obtained data was performed using variation statistics methods and an application package. Quantitative indicators are presented as mean (M) and standard deviation (SD). The Student's t-test was used to assess the significance of differences between groups. Differences were considered statistically significant at a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Research results. The study found that the frequency of detection of pathological changes during ultrasound examination of the fetus varied significantly depending on the clinical group of those examined.

In pregnant women with a normal gestation (Group I), ultrasound parameters were consistent with gestational age in most cases. Abnormalities were detected in 8.9% of patients and were primarily functional or transient in nature, not requiring specialized intervention. Fetometry parameters were within normal limits, and uteroplacental blood flow parameters showed no significant deviations.

In Group II, pregnant women with risk factors had a significantly higher incidence of pathological changes, amounting to 27.5% ($p < 0.05$). The most common cause was intrauterine growth retardation, which occurred in 12.5% of patients and was manifested by a decrease in the main fetometric parameters relative to the gestational age. Uteroplacental blood flow disorders were detected in 10.0% of the examined women and were characterized by an increased resistance index in the uterine arteries. Signs of fetal macrosomia were noted in 5.0% of pregnant women, primarily due to excess body weight and metabolic disorders.

In Group III, pregnant women with established fetal pathologies, ultrasound diagnostics revealed a wide range of abnormalities. Congenital malformations were diagnosed in 31.2% of cases, with the most common defects affecting the central nervous system and cardiovascular system. Intrauterine growth retardation was detected in 26.3% of fetuses and was accompanied by a significant delay in fetometric parameters. Signs of chronic fetal

hypoxia were recorded in 18.7% of patients and were confirmed by changes in Doppler parameters. Fetoplacental blood flow disorders were detected in 23.8% of pregnant women and were characterized by pathological changes in the umbilical artery and middle cerebral artery of the fetus.

Analysis of Doppler data revealed a statistically significant increase in uterine artery vascular resistance indices in pregnant women in Groups II and III compared to Group I ($p < 0.01$), indicating the development of placental insufficiency. The most pronounced changes were observed in patients with comorbidities. An assessment of the diagnostic efficacy of the method revealed that the sensitivity of ultrasound in detecting congenital anomalies was 89.4%, and the specificity was 92.1%, confirming the method's high informative value in prenatal screening.

Thus, the obtained results demonstrate that the frequency and structure of detected disorders directly depend on the presence of risk factors and the initial condition of the pregnant woman, and the integrated use of echography and Doppler ultrasound significantly improves the accuracy of early diagnosis of fetal pathologies.

Discussion of results. The data obtained confirm the high diagnostic value of ultrasound in prenatal screening. The detection rate of pathologies is significantly higher in pregnant women with risk factors, which is consistent with data from international studies.

Doppler ultrasound is particularly important, allowing for the detection of hemodynamic disturbances before clinical manifestations. This enables timely preventive and therapeutic measures. The results also show that an integrated approach (fetometry + Doppler ultrasound + anatomical assessment) significantly improves diagnostic accuracy compared to the use of isolated methods.

Conclusions:

1. Ultrasound is a highly informative prenatal diagnostic method with high sensitivity and specificity.
2. The detection rate of fetal abnormalities is significantly higher in pregnant women with risk factors.
3. The use of Doppler ultrasound significantly improves the early diagnosis of fetoplacental blood flow disorders.
4. Comprehensive ultrasound examinations at different stages of pregnancy enable the timely detection of congenital anomalies and functional disorders in the fetus.
5. Improvements in ultrasound technology contribute to improved pregnancy prognosis and a reduction in perinatal complications..

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